

GENDER CATEGORY IN MODERN ENGLISH

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Abstract. this article deals with the gender in modern English language, tackle several problems of category of grammatical gender, identifying gender markers in language, and exemplified various from novels.

Keywords: *gender, grammatical gender, feminine, masculine, neutral, paradigmatic.*

In recent years, with the development of scientific linguistic thought, views on many linguistic phenomena have been revised. The achievements of modern linguistics in the field of the system of parts of speech, in particular, a more accurate understanding of the nature of the pronominal class of words, allowed us to rethink the approach to the interpretation of the category of the gender of the modern English language. - For a long time, Russian linguistics refused to recognize the grammatical status of this category, treating it as a semantic category, "constantly present in the minds of speakers".

The problem of identifying generic markers in modern English has its own rather remarkable and long history. The category of grammatical gender - masculine, feminine, neuter - was once inherent in the nouns of the Old English period.

So, M.A.Kolpakchi gives such examples from the Old English language:

mona - the moon, steorra - the star were masculine,

bricg - bridge, tigol - brick - feminine,

scip - ship, eage - eye - neuter.

It happened that the grammatical gender was in contradiction with the real gender: wlf - woman and mægden - girl were neuter words.

The category of the gender of nouns finally disappeared among many grammatical simplifications in the language of the second half of the XVII century. The masculine gender was preserved only for men, the feminine gender - for women, and all concepts and objects and even animals began to be considered neuter nouns, which is transmitted by the pronoun it.

Thus, the historical development of the morphological structure of the English language has led to the fact that the category of grammatical gender has been significantly modified [1].

In the process of linguistic evolution, the differences between female and male speech strategies were constantly considered from different positions, the conceptual and semantic parameters of generic universals in the language were opposed, the prospects for linguistic normalization of speech traditions in marking the genus of linguistic units were discussed.

Derived feminine forms today are marked with a suffix or some other morphological or lexical feature that distinguishes the feminine gender from the general one and in some cases partially duplicates the form of the original masculine gender. For example, man – woman, author – authoress.

A special place in the creation of the gender module is occupied by feminine markers of English nouns denoting people in the field of their professional activity. First of all, in this subgroup, it should be noted the traditional suffixes that formalize nouns of the corresponding semantics: -ess, -ette, -ine.

In the British version, the normative use allows hostess, waitress, governess, stewardess and others.

The need to clarify the gender identity in the context of works of art or in oral communication expands the gender range due to the parallel coexistence of the forms woman doctor, she-doctor, doctor, doctorine.

The expansion of the professional range for female representatives contributed to the appearance of nouns with the suffix – ette: astronette, cosmonette, aviarette, farmarette, pickette - woman striker (participant of protest-picketing), copette – woman police officer (policewoman). Similar formations are registered among the nominations in the field of show business: usherette, screenette, glamorette.

Summarizing what has been said, we note that the meaning of gender in English is transmitted, as a rule:

1. lexical meaning of the word: masculine gender - man, boy; feminine gender - woman, girl; neuter gender – table, house;
2. personal pronouns - he, she, it;
3. suffixes: -ess, -ine, -er, -ette;
4. compound nouns: a woman-doctor, a he-cousin [2].

The category of gender in English is one of the most controversial issues in grammar. The overwhelming majority of linguists hold the view that this category existed only in the Old English period. It is believed that since the

formal gender indicators of nouns disappeared by the end of the Middle English period and the noun no longer agrees with adjectives and verbs adjacent to it, the gender category no longer exists in English. It is argued that in English the biologically motivated generic division into masculine and feminine gender is reflected only by lexical means – special words or lexical affixes, cf.: man – woman, tiger – tigress, he-goat – she-goat, male nurse, etc.

Indeed, the category of gender in English differs from the category of gender in many other languages, for example, in Russian, French or German. From a linguistic point of view, the gender category can be either significant (natural, meaningful), conveying the real signs of the gender of the referents, or formal (arbitrary). In Russian and some other languages, the gender category is meaningful only for personal nouns, and for non-personal nouns, this category is formal, i.e. it does not correspond to the real biological content of the designated referent, cf.: hand – female gender, finger – male gender, body – cf. gender, although all these nouns denote parts of the body. In English, the gender category is meaningful for the entire class of nouns, because it reflects the real generic characteristics of the designated referent (or their absence/insignificance) [3]. The gender category is realized through the obligatory correlation of each noun with the personal pronouns of the 3rd person singular he, she or it: man - he, woman – she, tree, dog – it. For example: A woman was standing on the platform. She was wearing a hat. It was decorated with ribbons and flowers... Pronouns in English are grammatical generic classifiers [4].

The category of gender is realized through the paradigmatic correlation of two oppositions forming a hierarchy. The first opposition is general and opposes personal nouns that distinguish between masculine and feminine gender (man – he, woman – she), and all other non-personal nouns that belong to the middle gender (tree, dog – it). The second opposition is formed only by personal nouns: at the lower level, masculine and feminine nouns are opposed.

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